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COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF ANTI-ASTHMATIC DRUGS ON QUALITY OF LIFE AND COGNITIVE FUNCTION IN ASTHMATIC PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Background:

In the management of asthma, combination therapy has been observed to produce significant effect than monotherapy for the improvement of Quality of Life (QoL) and cognitive function.

Purpose of the Study:

To assess the Quality of Life and cognitive function in asthmatic patients receiving monotherapy and combination therapy of antiasthmatic drugs.

Methods:

This is an open comparative study conducted in 235 asthmatic patients of age 35-60 years for duration of 6 months. The RAND 36 scale was used for assessing Quality of Life and MMSE score for assessing cognitive function. The data obtained were analyzed with graph Pad Instat V 3.06 software, Inc USA with 0.05 level of significance.

Result:

Asthmatic patients who had undergone the combination therapy deriphylline with salbutamol showed improvement in body pain, social functioning, physical health and total RAND 36 score. This combination therapy showed significant improvement in social functioning than deriphylline with dexamethasone combination. None of this combination showed significant effect on MMSE scores

Conclusion

In this study, quality of life of asthmatic patients was significantly improved with the combination therapy deriphylline with salbutamol than deriphylline with dexamethasone. Either combination or monotherapy was not found to be effective in improving cognitive function in these patients.

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INTRODUCTION

Quality of Life is recognized as a multifactor variable and can be subdivided into different domains (symptomatic well-being, emotional, physical, work-social, cognitive and life satisfaction), which are generally explored by means of specific questionnaires or scales¹. In the medical setting it can be defined as “a concept encompassing a broad range of physical and psychological characteristics and limitations, which describe an individual's ability to function and to derive satisfaction from doing so”². So it has been recognized as an important health outcome. Although assessing Quality of Life is methodologically complex, valid and reliable tools are available and can be used with asthma patients³. Relatively little is known about the impact of asthma on health related Quality of Life, even with the existing epidemiological and economic literature on asthma⁴.

Reduced health related quality of life was found with asthma patients in association with younger age, lower education, region of living, co-morbidities, use of bronchodilators and inhaled corticosteroids⁵. Individual's perceptions of their quality of life may be affected not only by their illness but also by their therapy. Thus it is important that treatment goals should not only be directed towards improving physiological end point but also patient's physical and mental health (i.e. Quality of Life with overall goal of reducing the debilitating impact of asthma on patient's lives)⁴. Important objectives of antiasthmatic therapy are to control symptoms and minimize the impact of the disease on patient functioning⁶. Since the changes in the airways are chronic and partially reversible, treatment of disease includes single or combined bronchodilators⁷. Combination therapy has been observed to provide significantly greater improvement than monotherapy in various studies⁸. In another study, the authors suggested that oxitropium bromide alone or in combination with theophylline improved life quality better than theophylline alone⁹. Cognitive dysfunction is an additional complication for the asthmatic patients. The free cortisol appeared to be associated with cognitive impairment and cortisol level after dexamethasone treatment increases the risk of cognitive decline¹⁰. In summary the available literature shows that asthma patients are affected with changes in Quality of Life and cognition.

The reports available at present on Quality of Life and cognitive function are carried out in European and western population. Only limited reports available from the Indian population.

Therefore the present study answers the following objectives.

- To assess the quality of life and cognitive function in asthmatic patients receiving anti asthmatic drugs (monotherapy and combination therapy) in south Indian population.

The Quality of Life and Cognitive function will be assessed by RAND 36 and MMSE questionnaire. The RAND 36 contains 36 items and eight scale levels and categorized in two domains as physical and mental health summary measures. The score ranges from 0-100, where 0 indicates poorer quality of life. Total score above 50 is considered as clinically significant quality of life. The MMSE scale contains 14 items and six scales. The MMSE contains assessment of orientation, registration, attention and calculation recall language and copying. The total score is 30 .A score of 24-30 indicates no cognitive impairment, score 18-23 indicates mild cognitive impairment and score of 0-17 indicates severe impairment.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials:

- Patient Demographic data form
- RAND 36 –Item Health Survey (Version 1.0)
- Folstien Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) scale

Methods:

Study site:

The study was conducted at C.S.I. Medical Mission Hospital, Neyyoor, Nagercoil and Primary Health Center, Kothanallor, Nagercoil, Tamil Nadu, South India. Patients enrolled into the study were asthmatics who visited the outpatient department.

Study design and duration:

It was designed as open comparative study in asthmatic patients for duration of 6 months.

Sample size:

235 asthmatic patients on anti asthmatic therapy without any co morbidities

Study drugs:

Deriphylline, Dexamethasone, Salbutamol

Study subjects

Inclusion criteria:

- No history of concomitant severe or chronic medical illness
- No history of depression or other major psychiatric disorder
- No history of psychosurgery or any other neurosurgical procedure.
- Patients taking only the above mentioned Antiasthmatic drugs

Exclusion criteria:

- Patients with previous cerebrovascular or cardio vascular disease, diabetes, uremia, hepatic or other metabolic & endocrine deficiencies, dementia, major depressive syndrome or psychiatric disorders.
- Pregnancy, Breast feeding females
- Participants who have received research medication within one month.
- Known or suspected hypersensitivity to study therapy or excipients.

RESULT

The present study was carried out in Out-Patient Department of the Medical Mission Hospital, Neyyoor and Primary Health Centre, Kothanalloor, Nagercoil, Tamil Nadu, India. 235 patients were enrolled according to the inclusion criteria. Enrolled patients were classified according to Sociodemographic (age, gender, and income), life style (smoker), food habits (vegetarian and non-vegetarian) and medical variable (asthmatic). All these patients were under therapy. The description of the total study population is represented in (Table No: 1).

The female patients under anti-asthmatic therapy showed significant decrease in total RAND 36 score, but no significant change was observed in MMSE scores (Table No: 1). In general, all other age groups patients showed significant decrease in total RAND 36 score and in MMSE scores on comparison with 35-40 years of age group (Table No: 1).

Literates showed significant increase in total RAND 36 scores and MMSE scores in comparison to illiterates (Table No: 1). No significant difference was observed in total RAND 36 score and MMSE score of Smokers in comparison with non- smokers (Table No: 1). No significant difference was observed in total RAND 36 and MMSE scores in income group with less than Rs.1000 in comparison with income group above Rs.1000 (Table No: 1).

Effect of antiasthmatic drugs on RAND 36 scale & MMSE score:

Among the 235 asthmatic patients, 72 received deriphylline and 107 patients received deriphylline with dexamethasone and 56 patients received deriphylline with Salbutamol (Table No: 1). The effect of different antiasthmatic therapy on RAND 36 and MMSE score in asthmatic patients is represented in Table no 2. The results indicate that, deriphylline with dexamethasone showed significant improvement in body pain in comparison to deriphylline. No significant difference was observed between deriphylline and deriphylline with dexamethasone in other domains of RAND 36 score and in MMSE score. In comparison with deriphylline, deriphylline with salbutamol showed significant improvement in body pain, social functioning, physical health domain and total RAND 36 scale. In comparison with deriphylline with dexamethasone, deriphylline with salbutamol showed significant improvement in social functioning. No significant difference was observed in MMSE scores.

Effect of Anti asthmatic drugs on RAND 36 Scale and MMSE scores on gender:

In this category the asthmatic male patients were divided according to their medication, no significant

difference was noted in the RAND 36 score and MMSE score except in physical function were deriphylline with salbutamol showed significantly decreased score, in comparison with male patients with deriphylline therapy only. In social functioning deriphylline with salbutamol showed significant improvement, in comparison with deriphylline. In physical function male patients receiving deriphylline showed significant improvement in comparison with those received combination of deriphylline with dexamethasone. No significant difference was observed in other domains of RAND 36 score and in MMSE score (Table No: 3).

The females were also grouped according to the type of drug they were administered. In this category deriphylline with dexamethasone showed significant improvement in body pain in comparison with deriphylline. In comparison with deriphylline, deriphylline with salbutamol showed significant improvement in body pain, social functioning, physical health and total Rand 36 score. They also showed significant increase in social functioning, total mental health and total RAND 36 score in comparison with deriphylline with dexamethasone. No significant change in MMSE scores was found between these drugs in female asthmatic patients (Table No: 3).

Effect of Anti asthmatic drugs on RAND 36 score and MMSE scores in different age groups of asthmatic patients:

Asthmatic patients with 51-60 years of age under deriphylline with dexamethasone therapy showed significant improvement in body pain, general health, physical health and total RAND 36 score (Table No: 4). Asthmatic patients above 60 years of age under deriphylline and Salbutamol therapy showed significant increase in social functioning, total mental health and total Rand 36 in comparison with deriphylline. Patients under deriphylline with Salbutamol therapy showed significant increase total mental health and total RAND 36 score. A significant increase in MMSE score was observed in comparisons of deriphylline with dexamethasone therapy (Table No: 5).

DISCUSSION

In our present study 235 asthmatic patients were enrolled according to our inclusion criteria. They were categorized according to sociodemographic, life style, food habits and medical variable. The two third of the study population constituted of females. Females have shown significant decrease in mental health in comparison with males. The decreased function in mental health in female even after the treatment with anti asthmatic drugs is not properly understood, but it may be due the presence of other medical complication like depression which is prevalent in middle aged asthmatic women may influence the Quality of Life in these patients. The physical activity had positive effects on Quality of Life for both men and women, but women had more preferable effects of maximum intensity on Quality of Life and resource utilization than men¹¹.

Total activity level was related independently to age and perceived health status. The elderly may have lower total activity scores for two reasons: Elderly people really do have a less varied life, because it seems possible that elderly people are engaging in less outside activities and therefore have a less varied life. There were substantial differences in activity level as a function of age. Our findings suggest that Quality of Life judgements are based not only on the activities restricted, but also on emotional reactions to any restriction¹².

It has previously been proposed that age-related decrements in cognitive performance in healthy adults may be related to reductions in cerebral oxygenation, leading to impaired glucose metabolism and consequently neurological functioning¹³. If oxygen delivery is further compromised due to the effects of asthma, this might impinge upon cognition in elderly patients in an additive manner, and consequently be responsible for any performance decrements on the tasks completed in the current study. Evidence from studies of healthy participants supports the contention that age and asthma related impairments may be due to a decrease in oxygen availability/glucose metabolism. For example, lowering cerebral glucose metabolism through experimentally induced moderate hypoglycemia or hypoxemia has been shown to impair cognitive task performance in healthy adults in an age-related manner¹⁴. It is possible that such metabolic changes affect the speed of information processing in old age^{15,16,17,18} and age related impairments may simply be expressions of a general slowing of all cognitive operations^{19,20,21}.

We found that asthmatic patients above 50 years of age under antiasthmatic therapy showed significant decrease in physical function, general health, physical health, mental health domains; total RAND 36 scale and cognitive function as compared to asthmatic patients below 50 years of age. It shows that older aged asthmatic patients are having decreased Quality of Life and cognitive function. Our report confirms early findings²².

In our study combination of deriphylline with salbutamol therapy shows improvement in body pain, social functioning, total physical health and total RAND 36 score in comparison with deriphylline and deriphylline with dexamethasone therapy. Our reports are in accordance with previous results²³.

In male asthmatic patients, combination of deriphylline with salbutamol is having better effect than monotherapy (deriphylline) in improving the Quality of Life of these patients. But, both monotherapy and combination therapy did not have any effect in improving the cognitive function.

In female patients, combination of deriphylline with salbutamol therapy shows significant improvement in social functioning, total physical health, total mental health and total RAND 36 score in comparison with deriphylline and deriphylline with dexamethasone. In addition to antiasthmatic therapy patient counseling, health supplements may be helpful in improving their Quality of Life (Table No: 4).

In asthmatic patients above 60 years of age combination therapy of deriphylline with salbutamol showed better effect in improving the quality of life of these patients than the patients treated with deriphylline alone or with deriphylline with dexamethasone. Mono therapy and combination therapy failed to improve the MMSE scores of these patients in all these age groups. It shows that antiasthmatic drugs did not have any effect on cognition (Table No: 5).

Limitations

The duration of the study was for only 6 months and as a result sample size obtained was less to produce much more significant result. The non-compliance to the anti asthmatic drugs can also produce bias in the results. The methodology of using RAND 36 scale and MMSE score questionnaires can also produce (2-5%) bias in the result. The different types of dosage forms considered for the study also can produce apart of bias in the result.

Potential directions to future research:

The prevalence of asthma has been increasing since the early 1980's for all age, sex and racial groups. Despite better understanding of the disease process and improved treatment modalities, the increasing incidence and prevalence of asthma in many parts of the world continues to make it a global health concern. Relatively little is known about the impact of asthma on health related Quality of Life, even with the existing epidemiological and economic literature on asthma. So further studies have to be carried out for better assessment of the influence of treatment on Quality of Life and cognitive function to improve their health status.

CONCLUSION

In our study, it shows that Quality of Life of asthmatic patients was significantly improved with combination therapy (deriphylline and salbutamol) than monotherapy (deriphylline alone). In combination therapy, deriphylline with salbutamol showed better effect than combination of deriphylline with dexamethasone. From this it can be concluded that combination therapy alone is not important, but selection of combination drugs is more important for better Quality of Life in asthmatic patients.

Either monotherapy or combination therapy was found to be effective in improving the cognitive function of the asthmatic patients. So inclusion of cognitive behavioral therapy may be effective in improving the cognitive function in these patients. In patients above 50 years either monotherapy or combination therapy did not show any improvement on Quality of Life and cognitive function.

Table 1: Characteristics of anti asthmatic patients with n%, rand - 36 scales and MMSE scores

PATIENTS (N =235)	N(%)	RAND 36	MMSE
GENDER			
Male	89 (37.87)	52.85 ±5.22	17.18 ± 3.49
Female	146 (62.12)	52.67 ±8.17	17.52 ± 3.86
AGE			
35-40	35 (14.89)	75 ± 7.77	20 ± 3.20
41-50	29 (12.34)	53.10 ± 8.26	18.7 ± 3.11
51-60	49 (20.85)	51.92 ± 5.31	17.60 ± 3.91
>60	122 (51.91)	52.19 ± 7.33	16.38 ± 3.54
EDUCATION			
Illiterate	80 (34.04)	51.50 ± 8.22	14.98 ± 3.67
Literate	155 (65.95)	54.11 ±7.18	19.64 ± 2.71
INCOME			
<1000	140 (59.57)	52.44 ± 7.48	16.62 ± 3.84
>1000	95 (40.42)	53.02 ± 6.76	18.52 ± 3.29
SMOKING			
Yes	64 (27.23)	52.63 ± 4.89	16.92 ± 3.74
No	171(72.76)	52.70 ± 7.89	17.56 ± 3.73
DRUGS			
Deriphylline	72 (30.63)	51.31 ± 6.97	17.91 ± 3.71
Deriphylline+dexamethasone	107 (45.53)	52.54 ± 6.58	17.32 ± 3.59
Deriphylline+salbutamol	56 (23.82)	54.71 ± 8.16	16.87 ± 4.01

Table 2: Effect of Antiasthmatic drugs on rand -36 and MMSE

RAND SCALE DOMAINS	ANTIASTHMATIC DRUGS		
	DERIPHYLLINE (72)	DERIPHYLLINE+ DEXAMETHASONE (107)	DERIPHYLLINE+ SALBUTAMOL (56)
PHYSICAL FUNCTION	52.12 ± 16.09	52.75 ± 12.70	53.90 ± 15.11
ROLE PHYSICAL	20.69 ± 5.89	21.86 ± 9.53	24.54 ± 14.50
BODY PAIN	51.52 ± 11.55	56.74 ± 12.33 ^y	56.56 ± 10.62 ^y
GENERAL HEALTH	44.31 ± 11.56	47.50 ± 16.36	46.41 ± 12.16
VITALITY	62.98 ± 8.90	62.52 ± 7.93	63.36 ± 10.45
SOCIAL FUNCTIONING	59.06 ± 18.75	62.87 ± 24.22	70.22 ± 19.01 ^y
ROLE EMOTIONAL	53.33 ± 12.65	53.02 ± 14.83	58.78 ± 45.25
MENTAL HEALTH	63.00 ± 14.59	60.71 ± 11.13	59.78 ± 9.71
TOTAL PHYSICAL HEALTH	47.02 ± 9.67	48.74 ± 7.77	49.77 ± 8.45 ^x
TOTAL MENTAL HEALTH	56.54 ± 6.41	57.32 ± 7.95	58.41 ± 6.07
TOTAL RAND- 36	51.31 ± 6.97	52.54 ± 6.58	54.71 ± 8.16 ^y
MMSE SCORES	17.91 ± 3.71	17.32 ± 3.59	16.87 ± 4.01

Data express in mean ± SD, y: $p < 0.01$, compared with deriphylline, a : < 0.05 compared with deriphylline+dexamethasone. Figure in parenthesis indicate number of patients

Table 3: Effect of gender on anti asthmatic drugs

RAND 36 SCALE DOMAINS	DERIPHYLLINE(72)		DERIPHYLLINE+ DEXAMETHASONE (107)		DERIPHYLLINE+ SALBUTAMOL (56)	
	MALE (27)	FEMALE (45)	MALE (45)	FEMALE (62)	MALE (17)	FEMALE (39)
PHYSICAL FUNCTION	56.66 ± 16.46	49.51 ± 15.47	52.20 ± 11.61	52.5 ± 13.32	48.43 ± 7.00 ^x	56.15 ± 16.95
ROLE PHYSICAL	21.85 ± 9.62	25.55 ± 11.32	23.48 ± 12.88	20.81 ± 6.40	26.25 ± 17.07	23.84 ± 13.49
BODY PAIN	52.74 ± 10.98	51.04 ± 12.26	55.04 ± 11.31	56.95 ± 11.98 ^x	52.75 ± 7.66	58.12 ± 11.34 ^y
GENERAL HEALTH	43.40 ± 9.36	44.97 ± 12.79	45.48 ± 12.31	47.12 ± 18.70	46.25 ± 8.85	46.48 ± 13.38
VITALITY	63.33 ± 7.33	62.44 ± 9.80	61.27 ± 8.38	62.98 ± 8.51	61.56 ± 12.61	64.10 ± 9.51
SOCIAL FUNCTIONING	59.35 ± 17.57	58.05 ± 18.26	70.87 ± 24.60	58.50 ± 20.78	75.46 ± 17.05 ^y	68.07 ± 19.56 ^{xa}
ROLE EMOTIONAL	53.33 ± 1.45	53.33 ± 7.19	50.23 ± 9.79	51.93 ± 5.87	53.33 ± 8.53	52.15 ± 5.28
MENTAL HEALTH	64.14 ± 12.07	63.11 ± 17.15	62.69 ± 11.23	58.25 ± 10.95	60.75 ± 9.26	59.38 ± 9.99
TOTAL PHYSICAL HEALTH	47.6 ± 6.76	46.70 ± 11.12	48.66 ± 7.98	48.88 ± 9.00	47.05 ± 5.73	50.89 ± 9.17 ^y
TOTAL MENTAL HEALTH	56.71 ± 6.39	56.38 ± 6.40	58.11 ± 7.33	56.25 ± 8.88	59.47 ± 5.89	59.81 ± 11.91 ^a
TOTAL RAND- 36	51.85 ± 5.81	51.00 ± 7.64	53.39 ± 5.69	51.94 ± 7.43	53.10 ± 4.30	55.37 ± 9.26 ^{yb}
MMSE SCORES	17.37 ± 3.79	18.13 ± 3.65	17.60 ± 2.95	17.20 ± 3.89	16.00 ± 3.81	17.23 ± 4.09

Data express in mean ± SD, y: $p < 0.01$, x: $p < 0.05$, compared with deriphylline in male and female, b: < 0.01 , a: < 0.05 compared with deriphylline+dexamethasone in male and female. Figure in parenthesis indicate number of patient

Table 4: Effects of antiasthmatic treatment on rand 36 scale and MMSE score (51 to 60)

AGE 51 To 60 YEARS			
RAND 36 SCALE DOMAINS	DERIPHYLLINE (20)	DERIPHYLLINE+ DEXAMETHASONE (26)	DERIPHYLLINE+ SALBUTAMOL(10)
PHYSICAL FUNCTION	51.15 ± 16.04	51.59 ± 9.80	53.33 ± 12.24
ROLE PHYSICAL	20 ± 11.43	22.27 ± 10.66	20 ± 11.39
BODY PAIN	50.05 ± 11.68	58.81 ± 9.50 ^y	57.88 ± 9.58
GENERAL HEALTH	41.75 ± 12.27	46.40 ± 10.00 ^x	50 ± 15.81
VITALITY	59.75 ± 10.06	62.5 ± 6.85	61.66 ± 10.60
SOCIAL FUNCTIONING	62.5 ± 20.83	63.75 ± 23.06	71.38 ± 15.86
ROLE EMOTIONAL	53.33 ± 6.53	51.81 ± 7.10	53.33 ± 9.54
MENTAL HEALTH	60.4 ± 10.37	64.72 ± 8.43	56.88 ± 9.11
TOTAL PHYSICAL HEALTH	44.25 ± 7.13	48.13 ± 4.99 ^y	48.33 ± 5.61
TOTAL MENTAL HEALTH	55.54 ± 6.86	57.84 ± 6.19	58.65 ± 6.61
TOTAL RAND-36	49.86 ± 5.30	52.68 ± 5.19 ^x	52.88 ± 5.56
MMSE	18.45 ± 2.94	16.59 ± 4.50	18.44 ± 3.81

Data express in mean ± SD, y: $p < 0.01$, x: $p < 0.05$, compared with deriphylline in male and female, b: < 0.01 , a: < 0.05 compared with deriphylline+dexamethasone in male and female. Figure in parenthesis indicate number of patient

Table 5: Effects of antiasthmatic treatment on rand -36 and MMSE (Above 60)

AGE > 60 YEARS			
RAND SCALES	DERIPHYLLINE (37)	DERIPHYLLINE+ DEXAMETHASONE (45)	DERIPHYLLINE+ SALBUTAMOL (24)
PHYSICAL FUNCTION	48.51 ± 15.35	49.5 ± 11.91	47.91 ± 8.45
ROLE PHYSICAL	21.35 ± 8.21	22.5 ± 11.03	22.08 ± 10.20
BODY PAIN	50.48 ± 11.29	54.57 ± 11.83	54.66 ± 10.89
GENERAL HEALTH	41.72 ± 10.31	42.3 ± 10.66	45.91 ± 11.10
VITALITY	63.37 ± 7.99	63 ± 6.58	62.91 ± 12.50
SOCIAL FUNCTIONING	59.86 ± 18.36	67.81 ± 25.61	77.29 ± 17.25z
ROLE EMOTIONAL	53.33 ± 11.35	55 ± 22.58	58.47 ± 45.33
MENTAL HEALTH	61.94 ± 12.56	59.3 ± 12.11	61.66 ± 10.27
TOTAL PHYSICAL HEALTH	45.09 ± 6.69	46.37 ± 6.41	48.57 ± 9.00
TOTAL MENTAL HEALTH	56.05 ± 6.24	57.48 ± 7.89	63.00 ± 13.67ya
TOTAL RAND-36	50.07 ± 5.83	51.74 ± 6.94	56.13 ± 9.68ya
MMSE	16.51 ± 3.89	16.5 ± 2.69	14.75 ± 3.62a

Data express in mean ± SD z: p<0.001, y: p<0.01, compared with deriphylline, a < 0.05 compared with deriphylline+dexamethasone. Figure in parenthesis indicate number of patients.

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